

MODEL OF GROWTH A IRREGULAR EUTECTICS COMPOSITE *IN SITU* (MMCs)

Edward Guzik

Faculty of Foundry Engineering , University of Mining and Metallurgy,
Reymonta 23 Street, 30-059 Kraków, Poland

SUMMARY: In the part comprising the author's own investigations a model of irregular eutectic growth; faceted / non-faceted (irregular composite *in situ*) crystallizing in such significant alloys as Fe-C and Al-Si has been presented. For the experimental verification of the elaborated model the results of the unidirectional crystallization of the irregular eutectic under in the Fe-C alloys were utilized. In the structure of the oriented graphite eutectic, the decreasing of the interlamellar spacing λ and the protrusion l of the austenite by the leading phase graphite with the increase of growth rate v were observed. A comparison of measured and calculated average λ values for pure $(\gamma)\text{Fe}$ - Graphite eutectic reveals good agreement. The developed model also indicates the influence direction of the material constants of the graphite eutectic on the interlamellar spacing and protrusion on the leading phase - graphite. It was stated that such material constants as wetting angle, diffusion coefficient and Gibbs - Thomson coefficient are of great importance in the eutectic growth

KEYWORDS : irregular eutectic, irregular composite *in situ*, interlamellar spacing of eutectic, unidirectional crystallization, graphite eutectic.

INTRODUCTION

Eutectic alloys have relatively low melting points, excellent fluidity, and good mechanical properties. Consequently, a broad spectrum of eutectic alloys has been developed and is available for different applications. According to the literature, there are roughly 3900 binary eutectics [1], but this number can be substantially increased when one considers multi-component systems. At the present, the microstructure of approximately 300 eutectic systems is known. Unidirectionally solidified eutectics (also known as composites *in situ*) are playing an increasingly important role in the development of new materials of the group „High technology”. Among many different kinds of eutectics microstructures: non - faceted / non - faceted (regular) and non - faceted / faceted (irregular) are the best known. The first is typical of metal - metal systems (a low melting entropy of the two phases) and the second is characteristic of the two important casting alloys, Fe - C and Al - Si (the one phase with a high melting entropy; graphite and silicon). Many researches have studied eutectic stable growth both theoretically and experimentally. One of these contributions was given Jackson and Hunt

[2], who set up a mathematical model for stable growth of eutectic with isothermal growing interface:

$$\Delta T = K_1 v \lambda_1 + K_2 / \lambda \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda_1^2 v = K_2 / K_1 = \text{const} \quad (2)$$

where ΔT is the supercooling of the interface, λ the lamellar or inter- fibre spacing, v the growth rate, and K_1 and K_2 can be evaluated from phase diagram and thermodynamic data

$$K_1 = \frac{\bar{m} C_0 P}{f_\alpha f_\beta} D \quad \text{and} \quad K_2 = 2\bar{m} \left(\frac{\Gamma_\alpha \sin \Theta_\alpha}{f_\alpha |m_\alpha|} + \frac{\Gamma_\beta \sin \Theta_\beta}{f_\beta m_\beta} \right)$$

with $\bar{m} = \frac{|m_\alpha| \cdot m_\beta}{|m_\alpha| + m_\beta}$, $\Gamma_i = \sigma_i / \Delta S^i$,

where m_α and m_β liquid slopes, C_0 concentration difference („length”) of eutectic tie - line, Γ Gibbs - Thomson coefficient, Θ wetting angle, f volume fraction, m liquidus slope, P function of volume fraction (see [2]), D diffusion coefficient in liquid, σ surface energy, ΔS volumetric entropy of fusion, i index for α or β phase.

The equation (2) describe rather well the growth of regular eutectic, e.g. Al - Cu and Sn - Pb. For irregular eutectic systems, the experimental average values of λ obtained at a given growth rate v are significantly higher than predicted by equation (2). Irregular eutectics (e.g. Fe - C, Al - Si) characterized by the presence of a faceted phase, whose growth kinetics are strongly affected by planar defect mechanisms („stiffness” of growth) and therefore they are very anisotropic. A average spacing will then be determined by the ability of graphite or Si to branch or to produce a new flake to fill the gap. Growth of irregular eutectic has been studied theoretically by several authors. For an irregular eutectic, the well - known and quite often quoted in literature is the model developed by Magnin and Kurz in 1987 [3] :

$$\langle \lambda \rangle^2 v = \phi^2 K_2 / K_1 \quad (3)$$

where ϕ is a constant for a given system, e.g. Fe - C, $\phi = 5.4$ and Al - Si, $\phi = 2.3$ [4].

In the paper theoretical (analytical) model of irregular composites in situ (oriented eutectic) are presented. The model takes into consideration the essential role of the faceted phase as the leading phase in the crystallization of such eutectic kind.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The lamellar growth irregular eutectic (non - faceted / faceted type; nf - f) will be cooperative, and the supposed solid - liquid interface profile is schematically shown in Fig. 1; where z is the depth of the depression in the nonfaceted phase α and l is the protrusion of the leading faceted phase β . The shape of the eutectic interface is described by the biquadratic even function

$$f(x) = ax^4 + bx^2 + c \quad (4)$$

If the imposed temperature gradient in the liquid (G), is constant over the solid - liquid interface, the non - isothermal coupling condition can be expressed as [2]

$$\frac{1}{S_\beta} \int_{-S_\beta}^0 [\Delta T_c(x) + \Delta T_r(x) + Gf_1(x)] dx = \frac{1}{S_\alpha} \int_0^{S_\alpha} [\Delta T_c(x) + \Delta T_r(x) + Gf_2(x)] dx = \overline{\Delta T} \quad (5)$$

where

$\Delta T_c(x)$ is the interface undercooling for solute diffusion [2];

$$\Delta T_c(x) = m_i [C_e - C(x, y = 0)], \quad (6)$$

and $\Delta T_r(x)$ is the undercooling due to interface curvature [2].

$$\Delta T_r(x) = -\Gamma_i \frac{d^2 f / dx^2}{\left[1 + \left(df/dx\right)^2\right]^{3/2}}, \quad (7)$$

The shape of solid - liquid interface eutectic (parameters z and l) in the two - dimensional model are written as:

$$f_1(x) = \left[\frac{16l}{\lambda^4 f_\beta^4} - \frac{4 \tan \Theta_\beta}{\lambda^3 f_\beta^3} \right] \cdot (x + S_\beta)^4 + \left(\frac{\tan \Theta_\beta}{\lambda f_\beta} - \frac{8l}{\lambda^2 f_\beta^2} \right) (x + S_\beta)^2 + l \quad (8a)$$

$$f_2(x) = \left(\frac{4 \tan \Theta_\alpha}{\lambda^3 f_\alpha^3} - \frac{16z}{\lambda^4 f_\alpha^4} \right) \cdot (x - S_\alpha)^4 + \left(\frac{8z}{\lambda^2 f_\alpha^2} - \frac{3 \tan \Theta_\alpha}{\lambda f_\alpha} \right) (x - S_\alpha)^2 - z \quad (8b)$$

where

parameters z and l as well as $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$ shown in Fig. 1; C_e - eutectic concentration.

Fig. 1: Schemat of irregular (lamellar) eutectic growth and solid - liquid interface; $\lambda = 2(S_\alpha + S_\beta)$, Θ_β and Θ_α are the contacting angles of phases at the conjunction point

Substituting equations 6 to 8 into 5 gives

$$\bar{\Delta T}_\alpha = -m_\alpha \left(\Delta C_\infty + B_0 + \frac{\lambda \nu C_0}{f_\alpha D} P_\alpha \right) + \frac{2\Gamma_\alpha \sin \Theta_\alpha}{f_\alpha \lambda} + \left(-\frac{Gtg\Theta_\alpha \lambda f_\alpha}{1,5} - \frac{8Gz}{15} \right) \quad (9a)$$

$$\bar{\Delta T}_\beta = -m_\beta \left(\Delta C_\infty + B_0 - \frac{\lambda \nu C}{f_\beta D} P_\beta \right) + \frac{2\Gamma \sin \Theta_\beta}{f_\beta \lambda} + \left(\frac{8Gl}{15} + \frac{Gtg\Theta_\beta \lambda f_\beta}{30} \right) \quad (9b)$$

where P is given by [2].

Multiplying Eqn 9a by m_β and Eqn 9b by m_α , and subtracting one from the other leads to

$$\bar{\Delta T} = K_1 \lambda \nu + K_2 / \lambda + E \quad (10)$$

where

$$E = \bar{m}G \left(\frac{\frac{8z}{15} + \frac{\lambda f_\alpha tg\Theta_\alpha}{1,5}}{|m_\alpha|} + \frac{\frac{8l}{15} + \frac{\lambda f_\beta tg\Theta_\beta}{30}}{m_\beta} \right) \quad (10a)$$

The parameters z and l must be calculated as a function of λ , ν and G . This can be done by constraining each phase, a new condition similar to Eqn 5, at its centre [3]

$$\Delta T_c(x = S_\alpha) + \Delta T_r(x = S_\alpha) - Gz = \frac{1}{S_\alpha} \int_0^{S_\alpha} [\Delta T_c(x) + \Delta T_r(x) + Gf_2(x)] dx \quad (11a)$$

$$\Delta T_c(x = -S_\beta) + \Delta T_r(x = -S_\beta) + Gl = \frac{1}{S_\beta} \int_{-S_\beta}^0 [\Delta T_c(x) + \Delta T_r(x) + Gf_1(x)] dx \quad (11b)$$

One can write ; (for $P_\alpha = P_\beta$)

$$-m_\alpha \left(\Delta C_\infty + B_0 + \frac{\lambda \nu C_0 \Pi'_\alpha}{D} \right) - 2\Gamma_\alpha \left(\frac{8z}{\lambda^2 f_\alpha^2} - \frac{3tg\Theta_\alpha}{\lambda f_\alpha} \right) - Gz = \Delta \bar{T}_\alpha \quad (12a)$$

$$-m_\beta \left(\Delta C_\infty + B - \frac{\lambda \nu C_0 \Pi'_\beta}{D} \right) - 2\Gamma_\beta \left(\frac{tg\Theta_\beta}{\lambda f_\beta} - \frac{8l}{\lambda^2 f'_\beta} \right) + Gl = \Delta \bar{T}_\beta \quad (12b)$$

Where Π' is given by (see Table 1) [3].

Setting Eqn 9 equal to Eqn 12 gives the depth of the depression in α phase and the protrusion of the leading faceted β phase

$$z = \frac{15f_\alpha^2}{7G\lambda^2 f_\alpha^2 + 240\Gamma_\alpha} \left[\left(\frac{|m_\alpha| C_0 \nu}{D} \left(\Pi'_\alpha - \frac{P}{f_\alpha} \right) + \frac{Gf_\alpha tg\Theta_\alpha}{1,5} \right) \lambda^3 + \frac{2\Gamma_\alpha \lambda}{f_\alpha} (3tg\Theta_\alpha - \sin \Theta_\alpha) \right] \quad (13a)$$

$$l = \frac{15f_\beta^2}{7G\lambda^2 f_\beta^2 + 240\Gamma_\beta} \left[\left(\frac{m_\beta C_0 v}{D} \left(\Pi'_\beta - \frac{P}{f_\beta} \right) + \frac{Gf_\beta \text{tg}\Theta_\beta}{30} \right) \lambda^3 + \frac{2\Gamma_\beta \lambda}{f_\beta} (\text{tg}\Theta_\beta + \sin\Theta_\beta) \right] \quad (13b)$$

Substituting Eqn 13 into Eqn 10 one then obtains

$$\bar{\Delta T} = K_1 \lambda v + K_2 / \lambda + GE' \lambda + G^2 E'' \lambda^3 + GE''' \lambda^3 v \quad (14)$$

where

$$E' = \bar{m} \left[\frac{16f_\alpha \Gamma_\alpha (3\text{tg}\Theta_\alpha - \sin\Theta_\alpha)}{|m_\alpha| (7G\lambda^2 f_\alpha^2 + 240\Gamma_\alpha)} + \frac{f_\alpha \text{tg}\Theta_\alpha}{1,5|m_\alpha|} + \frac{f_\beta \text{tg}\Theta_\beta}{30m_\beta} + \frac{16f_\beta \Gamma_\beta (\text{tg}\Theta_\beta + \sin\Theta_\beta)}{m_\beta (7G\lambda^2 f_\beta^2 + 240\Gamma_\beta)} \right],$$

$$E'' = \bar{m} \left[\frac{8f_\alpha^3 \text{tg}\Theta_\alpha}{1,5|m_\alpha| (7G\lambda^2 f_\alpha^2 + 240\Gamma_\alpha)} + \frac{8f_\beta^3 \text{tg}\Theta_\beta}{30m_\beta (7G\lambda^2 f_\beta^2 + 240\Gamma_\beta)} \right],$$

$$E''' = \frac{8\bar{m}C_0}{D} \cdot \left(\frac{f_\alpha^2 \Pi'_\alpha - f_\alpha P}{7G\lambda^2 f_\alpha^2 + 240\Gamma_\alpha} + \frac{f_\beta^2 \Pi'_\beta - f_\beta P}{7G\lambda^2 f_\beta^2 + 240\Gamma_\beta} \right).$$

The operative points („operating range”[3]) on the growth curve is defined using a morphological criterion to characterize the branching behaviour of the faceted phase. Differentiation ($\{d(\Delta T) / d\lambda\}_{v=const} = 0$ [5]) of Eqn 14 (for $G\lambda^2 f^2 / 240 \Gamma < 1$ [3]) leads to basic relationship on which the growth of the irregular composit *in situ* (irregular eutectic) depends

$$3\langle \lambda \rangle^4 (G^2 E'' + GE''' v) + \phi'^2 \langle \lambda \rangle^2 (K_1 v + GE') = K_2 \phi'^4 \quad (15)$$

and

$$\bar{\lambda} = \left[0,5 + \left(\frac{\lambda'}{\lambda_1} \right)^{0,5} \right] \left(\frac{-K_1 v + GE'}{6(G^2 E'' + GE''' v)} \right)^{0,5}$$

where

$$\lambda' = \frac{30\Gamma_\beta \cos\Theta_\beta}{\frac{15f_\beta v C_0 m_\beta}{D \text{tg}\Theta_\beta} \left(\Pi'_\beta - \frac{P}{f_\beta} \right) + 0,842 f_\beta^2 G}$$

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{2D}{C_0 P v} \left(\frac{f_\beta \Gamma_\alpha \sin\Theta_\alpha}{|m_\alpha|} + \frac{f_\alpha \Gamma_\beta \sin\Theta_\beta}{m_\beta} \right)$$

A new interpretation of the irregular eutectic (composit) growth theory (Eqn 15) is proposed.

TEST RESULTS AND THEIR ANALYSIS

For the experimental verification of the elaborated model the results of the unidirectional solidification of the eutectic under question as well as observations of the „frozen” solid - liquid interface of the graphite eutectic in the $\gamma(\text{Fe}) - 4,28\% \text{C}$ alloys were utilized. The investigated Fe-C alloy was produced in a Balzers vacuum using high - purity Fe and spectrographically pure graphite. Unidirectional solidification of the eutectic alloys was carried out in a Bridgman apparatus. Construction design details of this unit are given elsewhere [6]. The drive mechanism of the furnace operating chamber has been started after the temperature has been stabilized on the level of 1723 K. The temperature gradient in the liquid metal just preceding the solid/liquid interface was 195 K/cm.

Figure 2 shows microstructure of quenched growing interface morphology of $\gamma(\text{Fe}) - \text{C}$ graphite eutectic under stable growth condition. In the microstructure of the unidirectional graphite eutectic, crystallizing with the rate v in the range from 0.138 to $3.33 \cdot 10^{-4}$ cm/s, the decreasing of the parameter λ (interlamellar spacing) and the protrusion l of the austenite by leading phase graphite with the increase of v were observed.

Fig. 2: Microstructures and shape solid-liquid interface obtained in irregular oriented graphite eutectic (c and d - the parameters λ_1 and λ_2 , see in Fig. 1)

Table 1: Physical properties of the (γ) Fe - Graphite eutectic alloy

	Notation	Unit	Austenite	Graphite (β)
Eutectic concentration	C_{eut}	wt%	4.26	
Concentration	C_o	wt%	97.9	
Eutectic temperature	T_e	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	1154	
Liquides slope	m_i	K/wt%	-135	400
Interdiffusion coefficient in liquid	D	cm^2/s	0.0000125	
Gibbs-Thomson coefficient	Γ_i	K·cm	0.000019	0.000037
Volume fraction	f_i	—	0.926	0.074
Wetting angle	Θ_i	deg.	25	85
Function of volume fraction	P	—	0.004226	
Function of volume fraction	Π'	—	0.01628	0.05825

where:

$$P = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n\pi)} \cdot \sin(n\pi f), [2]$$

$$\Pi' = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n\pi)} \cdot \sin(n\pi f), [3]$$

Fig. 3. Relationship of interlamellar spacing λ of graphite eutectic and growth rate v and comparison with theoretical models: 1 [2], 2 [4], 3 [3], 4 [Eqn 15], 5 [7]

The experimental results of parameters λ are compared in Fig. 3 to the theoretical relationships (Eqn 15). Physical properties of pure Fe - C eutectic alloy used for calculations were summarized in Table 1. It was proved that the elaborated analytic model of the growth of the irregular eutectic, as compared with models described up to now in the literature [2, 3, 4, 7], allows to determine more precisely the interlamellar spacing λ in the graphite eutectic. Good agreement has been obtained between theory (new model of irregular eutectic growth) and interlamellar spacing λ measured in pure Fe - C eutectic alloys with lamellar structure.

CONCLUSIONS

An new analytical model (Eqn 15) which describes irregular eutectic (irregular composite *in situ*) growth is presented. It is based upon Jackson and Hunt (1996) and Magnin and Kurz (1987) treatments. The proposed shape of the solidification front of irregular eutectic, characterized by a suitable function as well as applying the non-isothermal solid - liquid interface for modeling purposes allows calculation of the characteristic depression in the nonfaced phase (e.g. austenite) and the protrusion of the leading phase (e.g. graphite). In the microstructure of the oriented graphite eutectic, the decreasing of the interlamellar spacing λ and the protrusion l of the austenite by the leading phase graphite with the increase of growth rate v were observed. Application of the model to the e.g. unidirectional graphite eutectic yields values for interlamellar spacing λ which are in good agreement with experiment.

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